

PR106 had less than 20% damage in one replication but more than 60% of its plot was completely destroyed in another replication. The same was true for PR445, PR560, PR561, and PR563.

A survey conducted by the Indian Directorate of Quarantine, Plant Protection, and Storage also revealed hopperburn on IR8 on farmers' fields in the Punjab in 1978. An objective of our future rice breeding programs is to develop WBPH-resistant varieties. □

Evaluation of rice strains for resistance to gall midge and leaf roller

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Rice entries received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project were screened for resistance to gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* and leaf roller

Hopperburn in PR558 rice, caused by WBPH in 1978 at the Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, India.

Cnaphalocrosis medinalis in a field trial laid out in a randomized block design at Madurai Agricultural College Farm in

1977-78. Of the 265 entries evaluated, 20 had minimum incidence of gall midge and leaf roller (see table). IET 6181, 6286, 6293, and 6195, on which the incidence of both gall midge and leaf roller was much lower than that on the susceptible varieties, appear to have some resistance to both insects. □

Rice entries resistant to gall midge and leaf roller, mean of two replications in 3 periods, Madurai, India.

IET no.	Designation	Parents	Tillers (%) affected by gall midge	Leaves (%) affected by leaf roller
<i>Resistant to both gall midge and leaf roller</i>				
6181	WGL20691	CR44/W12708	0.9	7.1
6286	CR 95-181-2	Leaung 152/IR8	0	9.3
6293	WGL 26445	—	0	8.8
6295	RNR 32341	—	0.4	7.9
<i>Resistant to gall midge</i>				
4600	RP 872-1-2	Cauvery/W12787	0	—
5700	IR2071-636-5-5	IR24/CR94-13	0.8	—
5703	HYN 17-5-4	Hoyoku/Zinya	0.5	—
5981	OR 100-7	Kumar/Bala	0.9	—
5116	RP894-5-1-5-4	CR44-35/W12708	0.5	—
5233	RP872-20-4-3-4	Cauvery/W12787	0.4	—
5711	RP974-173-4	Sona/RP9-4	0	—
6257	1140-47-2-46-19	—	0.3	—
2911	RPW 6-17	IR8/Siam 29	0.7	—
3347	ORS 46 1	Leaung 152//IR8*2	0	—
3354	RP350-57-1-1	820862/820916	0.2	—
3356	RP352-28-1-1-4	IR8/PTB18//Eswarakora/IR8	0	—
3362	RP9-10-3-2-1-1	IR8/W1251	0.7	—
6287	CR 95-26-1	Leaung 152/IR8	0.7	—
6292	WGL 26442	—	0.3	—
—	RPW 6-13	—	0.7	—
<i>Susceptible check</i>				
Jaya			17.2	60.1
Pankaj			12.0	—

Outbreak of rice thrips in Kuttanadu, Kerala, India

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The usual farming practice in Kuttanadu is to grow a single rice crop (locally called *punja*) from October to February. Farmers have recently attempted to grow a second rice crop from April to September, which is almost free of serious insect problems.

The rice thrip *Buliothrips biformis* has only recently become a serious punja-season pest, especially on the late crop. The transplanted crop suffered a serious thrip outbreak in May and June 1978. The main symptoms were leaf rolling and drying at the leaf tips. In severe infestations the plants were stunted and the lower leaves killed.

Observations of 15 varieties and lines

showed that some were seriously damaged. The percentage of infested leaves varied from 28.2 on the variety

Jyothi to 51.5 on Thriveni. That suggests that the thrip shows some varietal preference or nonpreference. The grass

Panicum repens, which grows abundantly on field bunds, is an alternate host for the insect. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Dry matter and nitrogen accumulation in two semidwarf indica rices in rainfed-upland conditions

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The accumulation of dry matter and nitrogen in two semidwarf indica rices, Padma and Bala, under rainfed-upland culture was studied in a field trial during the kharif (wet) season of 1972 and 1973 at the Crop Research Center of the G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar. Seeds were drilled in a dry seedbed at 60 kg/ha in rows 23 cm apart. Four nitrogen levels (30, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha) and 5 application methods were used.

Padma and Bala did not differ markedly in the accumulation of dry matter up to the heading stage (see fig. a). But interestingly, the rate of dry matter accumulation from heading to maturity was higher in Bala than in Padma. That indicates that Bala had better photosynthetic ability than Padma during the postheading period, which was probably the main reason for its higher dry matter accumulation and, consequently, higher grain yield at maturity (see table). Bala had higher concentrations of nitrogen than Padma at all growth stages except tillering in 1972 (fig. b). But in 1973 nitrogen concentration was higher in Bala only until heading; afterwards, that in Padma was higher. In both years, the nitrogen concentration in the plants of the two varieties decreased linearly from panicle initiation to 15 days after heading (DH), but in 1972 that in Padma decreased

Dry-matter yield (a), nitrogen concentration (b) and nitrogen uptake (c) at various stages of growth of two dwarf indica rices. T = tillering (40 DS), PI = panicle initiation (60 DS), H = heading (86 DS), 15 DH (days after heading, 101 DS), M = maturity (111 DS), DS = days after sowing.

linearly from tillering to 15 DH.

Bala plants absorbed more nitrogen from the soil than Padma plants at all growth stages in both years (fig. c). The difference was greater during the postheading period. The nitrogen uptake in Bala grains at maturity was higher than that in Padma, but that in Padma's straw

was higher (see table). Padma and Bala removed an average of 58 and 63 kg N/ha, respectively, at maturity. Bala translocated to its grains about 74% of the absorbed nitrogen; Padma translocated 69%. The data show that Bala performs better than Padma in rainfed-upland culture. □

Dry matter yield, nitrogen concentration, and nitrogen uptake at maturity in two semidwarf indica rices under rainfed-upland conditions. Pantnagar, India.

Particulars	Padma		Bala		S. Em.±		CD 5% ^b	
	1972	1973	1972	1973	1972	1973	1972	1973
Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	2.91	4.07	3.22	4.50	0.106	0.068	ns	0.205
Straw yield ^a (t/ha)	2.44	3.36	2.68	3.39	0.072	0.067	0.219	ns
N in grain (%)	1.10	1.18	1.20	1.22	0.011	0.009	0.034	0.029
N in straw (%)	0.66	0.64	0.55	0.52	0.007	0.009	0.020	0.028
N uptake of grain (kg/ha)	32.08	47.99	39.01	55.12	1.46	0.91	4.42	2.75
N uptake of straw (kg/ha)	15.19	21.42	14.88	17.68	0.44	0.63	ns	1.91
Total N uptake (kg/ha)	41.27	69.41	53.89	72.80	1.75	1.75	5.31	ns

^aA sum of grain and straw yields would represent total dry matter at maturity.

^bns = not significant.